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Drastic mobility restrictions during SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: An opportunity to learn about constraints on the way to a pollution-free city

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Abstract:	<p>Road traffic is one of the main sources of pollution in modern cities. If there is a desire to move towards healthier cities, it may be necessary to modify the current model of mobility. The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, together with the measures applied by most governments in the world to control the mobility of citizens, offered a unique opportunity to assess the changes in pollution levels after a drastic reduction in road traffic. In this study, air and noise pollution levels and road traffic flow were analysed in the city of Cáceres, Spain, before and during the state of emergency imposed by the Spanish government. The values obtained were compared with the quality limits established by both the Spanish government and the World Health Organization (WHO). A traffic noise prediction model has been employed to evaluate the acoustic impact resulting from the reduction in traffic flow. As a result of this study, it was found that air pollution was indeed reduced due to the mobility restrictions imposed to control the pandemic, but that the WHO's recommendations for the values of the day-evening-night noise indicator (Lden) and the night-time noise indicator (Ln) for road traffic noise, which should not be exceeded, were not met. These findings highlight the need to review current urban mobility models if the WHO's recommendations are to be reached in regard to reducing the effects of exposure of the population to urban noise.</p>	

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1 **Drastic mobility restrictions during SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: An opportunity to learn about constraints on the**
2 **way to a pollution-free city**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 Road traffic is one of the main sources of pollution in modern cities. If there is a desire to move towards
14 healthier cities, it may be necessary to modify the current model of mobility. The SARS-CoV-2
15 pandemic, together with the measures applied by most governments in the world to control the mobility
16 of citizens, offered a unique opportunity to assess the changes in pollution levels after a drastic reduction
17 in road traffic. In this study, air and noise pollution levels and road traffic flow were analysed in the city
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23 the WHO's recommendations for the values of the day-evening-night noise indicator (L_{den}) and the night-
24 time noise indicator (L_n) for road traffic noise, which should not be exceeded, were not met. These
25 findings highlight the need to review current urban mobility models if the WHO's recommendations are
26 to be reached in regard to reducing the effects of exposure of the population to urban noise.

27

28 Keywords: SARS-CoV-2 pandemic – Noise and air pollution – traffic flow – lockdown – action plans

29

30

31 **Introduction**

32

33 There are many articles that have studied the problems associated with road traffic, in terms of both the
34 noise and air pollution that this traffic generates (Adza et al. 2022; Fecht et al. 2016; Montes-González et
35 al. 2018a). The World Health Organization (WHO) has published several reports over the years highlighting
36 the health problems associated with both excessive noise pollution (e.g., WHO 2018) and the presence of
37 high concentrations of certain substances such as NO₂, O₃, SO₂, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ (WHO 2021), and has set
38 limits for these pollutants with the aim of achieving healthy environments. If these limits represent the ideal
39 for a healthy life in a city, it is reasonable to ask whether they are achievable in the usual ways in which
40 daily activities are carried out, whether economic or social.

41 At its 2015 General Assembly, the United Nations set out a series of goals for sustainable
42 development (United Nations 2015). Of the 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) that were proposed,
43 Goal 3 (*Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages*) and Goal 11 (*Make cities more*
44 *inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable*) will be considered in the present work. In this context, an
45 analysis will be conducted to determine whether it is possible to reduce existing noise and air

46 pollution in cities to make them healthier. As the United Nations has stated, increasing numbers of
47 people are now living in cities, and the rural-urban drift seems to be unstoppable (United Nations 2019).
48 This is accompanied by an increase in the flow of road traffic in cities. All of the studies carried out by
49 official organisations, such as the aforementioned reports published by the WHO or those of the European
50 Environmental Agency (2020; 2022), to mention only the most recent, indicate that if the current model of
51 development for cities continues, health problems will increase. [Therefore, if the enhancement of the](#)
52 [quality of life in cities is desired, among the various proposals available, one that must not be forgotten is](#)
53 [the reduction of dependence on private vehicles.](#)

54 Given the effects of noise on people's health, traffic noise prediction models have been used in
55 recent years to assess the acoustic impact of existing or future infrastructures. Several published studies are
56 concerned with the problem of choosing the right traffic noise simulation method (Patel, Kumar Sing &
57 Saw 2022; Wolniewicz & Zagubień 2015; Quartieri et al. 2009). The fine-tuning of these models is essential
58 for an accurate evaluation of the acoustic footprint of new facilities.

59 The question to be answered by city managers is how far the reliance on personal automobiles
60 would need to be reduced to achieve a healthy city. Several studies have proposed different city models
61 with the aim of rectifying this situation (Nieuwenhuijsen 2020; Mouratidis 2021; Yildirim et al. 2023).
62 [Amidst the different suggestions, one of the key proposals involves managing traffic flow, though the](#)
63 [primary challenge lies in determining the extent to which this traffic flow should be adjusted, without](#)
64 [noticeably affecting the economic activity carried out in the city, given the current interdependence between](#)
65 [this economic activity and urban mobility \(Dadashova et al. 2021; Patatoukas & Skabardonis 2016\).](#)
66 However, a recent global event in the form of the pandemic associated with the SARS-CoV-2 virus allows
67 us to find a possible answer. In an attempt to control its spread, governments in a large number of countries
68 took measures to reduce the clustering of people in workplaces, meeting places and even outdoors. These
69 measures led to a drastic reduction in the mobility of people, and thus the economic activity in cities. As a
70 result of this reduced mobility, road traffic fell dramatically. Studies carried out on all continents have
71 reported variations in noise or air pollution levels (e.g. Asensio et al. 2020; Rodríguez et al. 2022; Mishra
72 et al. 2021; Muhammad et al. 2020; Sharma et al. 2020). These papers have analysed variations in pollution
73 levels in cities or in the soundscape. Although some studies have been published on the effect of a reduction
74 in traffic flow on noise levels in a city (Hemker et al. 2023), in our opinion, it remains to be seen whether
75 this extreme situation led to a sufficient reduction in pollution levels (air or noise) to reach the limits
76 established by the WHO for living in a healthy environment. [Moreover, when creating noise maps through](#)
77 [computational techniques, sound measurements are crucial. They are needed not only for calibrating or](#)
78 [validating the model but also for confirming the accuracy of its predictions \(WG-AEN 2007\). Under normal](#)
79 [conditions, it is not possible to obtain a genuine reduction in traffic flow like that caused by the COVID-19](#)
80 [pandemic required for validation.](#)

81 This paper analyses the levels of noise and air pollution in the city of Cáceres during a temporal
82 period surrounding the lockdown imposed by the Spanish government (before, during, and after) and,
83 therefore, throughout the different stages it went through, in terms of the limits established by both the
84 WHO and the Spanish government itself. To observe the variations that occurred during the lockdown, the
85 measured values of noise level and air pollution [during almost](#) one and a half months prior to the declaration
86 of the state of emergency [\(from the 1st of February to the 13th of March\)](#) have been taken as a reference
87 for what could be considered a normal situation in the city. The variation in traffic flow or the number of
88 overnight stays in the city has also been considered as indicators of the change in economic activity during
89 the lockdown. [The obtained results have been used to evaluate the impact of a significant reduction in](#)
90 [mobility. This reduction, experienced during the mentioned lockdown, led to a substantial decline in](#)
91 [economic activity. The present work aims to determine whether this reduction is sufficient to attain the](#)
92 [enhancements in acoustic and air quality advocated by the authorities. It should be kept in mind the close](#)
93 [relationship between economic activity and traffic volume \(Dadashova et al. 2021; Patatoukas &](#)
94 [Skabardonis 2016\), as well as the fact that road traffic is the primary source of noise in cities worldwide](#)
95 [\(European Environment Agency 2020\). Therefore, a decrease in traffic flow and urban mobility will be](#)
96 [accompanied by a decline in economic activity. This reduction in traffic will result in a decrease in noise](#)
97 [levels and air pollution. During the lockdown imposed by the Spanish government, there was a clear decline](#)
98 [in economic activity, due to the mandated closure of nearly all direct customer-facing businesses and](#)
99 [restrictions on public movement without a valid reason. Thus, the per capita GDP in the city of Cáceres](#)

100 decreased from 20,393 € in 2019 to 18,553 € in 2020, a value lower than the per capita GDP in 2017
101 (National Institute of Statistics 2022). Additionally, data on the reduction in city traffic volume and mobility
102 are available. Therefore, an examination has been conducted to determine whether this reduction is
103 sufficient to meet the quality goals established by the authorities.

104

105 **Methodology**

106

107 Cáceres (39° 28' 28" N, 6° 22' 18" W) is a city of approximately 96,000 inhabitants (National Institute of
108 Statistics, 2021), although during the school year its population exceeds 100,000 inhabitants due to the
109 influx of an **important** number of university students. It is located in the centre of the Extremadura region,
110 in southwestern Spain (see Fig. 1a). Cáceres has an important historic centre, which has been declared a
111 World Heritage Site by UNESCO, and a large amount of green space (Barrigón Morillas et al. 2013; Rey-
112 Gozalo et al. 2019a). Its inhabitants possess about 75,000 vehicles (73 % cars, 13 % motorcycles, 12 %
113 heavy vehicles), according to data from the Cáceres City Council (2022). Although no updated official
114 statistics are available, the last survey on commuting to the workplace, which was carried out by the
115 National Institute of Statistics in 2011, showed a strong preference by the inhabitants for the use of private
116 vehicles (with 45.5 % travelling by car, 8.4 % by public transport, and 20.6 % on foot). This situation does
117 not seem to have reversed, given the annual increase in the number of vehicles registered in the city,
118 according to the data published on the website of the Cáceres City Council (2022). **The 85.57 % of the**
119 **population was employed in 2020 in the service sector, according to data from the National Institute of**
120 **Statistics (2021). Only 4.22% of the population was engaged in industrial activities (including those**
121 **working in the construction sector). There is only one company that can be considered an industry (with**
122 **around 240 employees), but it has fairly low levels of emissions of both noise and chemical pollutants, and**
123 **it is located more than 4 km away from downtown.**

124 Three long-term **sound level** measurement systems had been established in the city of Cáceres
125 before the mobility restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic declared on 14 March 2020 (see Fig. 1b).
126 The measurement points were selected in order to collect information in different areas of the city, and were
127 located in streets with a certain diversity in terms of their architectural and urban characteristics following
128 the categorization method. This method involves classifying urban roads according to their functionality as
129 communication routes (Rey-Gozalo et al. 2020). In the present study, the focus has been primarily on
130 analysing the temporal variation of noise levels rather than their spatial variation, although not completely
131 disregarding it. Point 1 in Fig. 1b represents an avenue in the city centre with one lane of traffic in each
132 direction, parking on both sides, a wide, landscaped central promenade, and a continuous flow of vehicles
133 during working hours. Point 2 corresponds to a street with one lane of traffic in each direction and parking
134 on both sides, in a residential neighbourhood, with several supermarkets nearby. Point 3 corresponds to a
135 street with a single lane of traffic and parking on both sides, in a residential area close to several bars and
136 nightclubs. If the urban road and streets of Cáceres are classified considering the Categorisation Method
137 (Barrigón Morillas et al. 2002; 2005a), point 1 would be located in a Category 3 street, point 2 in a Category
138 4 street, and point 3 in a Category 5 street.

139

140 (a)

141 (b)

142 **Fig. 1** (a) Location of the city of Cáceres; (b) locations of the measurement points within the city. Points
 143 1, 2, and 3 show the noise monitoring stations; Env. Station shows the air quality monitoring station.

144

145 Class 1 sound level meters with semi-outdoor systems were used as monitoring stations, and were
 146 mounted on residential buildings according to ISO 1996-2:2017 (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2016). Since the
 147 microphones were placed on balconies several metres above the ground, no acoustic screening effect was
 148 expected to arise from vehicles parked on the streets (Montes González et al. 2018b; 2020).

149 To study the impact of lockdown on environmental noise levels in Cáceres, data obtained from
 150 February 2020 to the end of June 2020 were considered in the analysis (on the 14th of March, a state of
 151 emergency was declared in Spain due to COVID-19, and on 22 June, the "new normal" started). Table 1
 152 shows the different phases of the lockdown, with the different degrees of mobility that were permitted
 153 during this period.

154

155 **Table 1** Duration of the different stages of lockdown considered in this study

Stage	Length	Description
A	2020/02/01 – 2020/03/13	Pre-COVID-19 period
B	2020/03/14 - 2020/03/29	State of emergency declared for the whole country: closure of schools, suspension of all types of events, closure of non-essential businesses (only large

		supermarkets or some specific services were allowed to open), prohibition of walks or outdoor sports practice
C	2020/03/30 – 2020/04/09	Conditions imposed in the previous period hardened, with a ban on attendance at work except for essential activities across the country
D	2020/04/10 – 2020/04/25	Return to the situation in Stage B
E	2020/04/26 – 2020/04/03	Walks and individual outdoor sports practice allowed
F	2020/05/04 – 2020/05/10	Beginning of the process back to normal Phase 0: Small shops (by appointment) and take-away restaurants allowed to open
G	2020/05/11 – 2020/05/24	Phase 1: Bar terraces allowed to open with occupancy limitations; places of worship allowed to open with a capacity limit of one third; small shops allowed to open with capacity limitations.
H	2020/05/25 – 2020/06/07	Phase 2: Voluntary opening of infant education up to six years of age and the final years of non-university education. Expansion of the capacity of small businesses. People allowed to enter restaurants, but only seated and with limited capacity. Expansion of the capacity of terraces. Re-opening of shows and cultural activities with limitations. Nightlife venues closed.
I	2020/06/08 – 2020/06/21	Phase 3: New increases in the capacity of small businesses. New increases in the capacity of restaurants and bar service. Restaurants with terraces allowed to open 50 % of the tables permitted in previous years based on their municipal licences. Opening of discos and night bars with limited capacity, with dancing prohibited. Closing time set at 1:00 am.
J	2020/06/22 – 2020/06/30	New normal

156

157 The Spanish government (2023) declared a state of emergency throughout the country on 14 March
158 2020, initially for 15 days, with strong measures that severely restricted the movement of people and
159 economic activity. This situation lasted until 2 May, when the "de-escalation" process started; this took
160 place in different phases (from phase 0 to phase 3) until 22 June, which is when the "new normal" began.
161 This was quite different from life in early March, with mandatory masks, a mandatory safety distance of
162 1.5 m, and strict capacity limitations for enclosed spaces, although all economic activity was functioning.
163 The lockdown and capacity reduction measures in shops, bars, etc. severely affected the city's economy.
164 As mentioned above, 85 % – 86 % of the population was employed in the service sector, and this was the
165 sector most affected by the restrictions.

166 Day (L_d), evening (L_e), night-time (L_n) and day-evening-night (L_{den}) noise indicators were
167 calculated for each day of the period under study (ISO 1996-1:2016). L_d is the equivalent continuous sound
168 pressure level when the reference time interval is the day, the 12 h between 7 h and 19 h. L_e is the equivalent
169 continuous sound pressure level when the reference time interval is the evening, the 4 h between 19 h and
170 23 h. L_n is the equivalent continuous sound pressure level when the reference time interval is the night, the
171 8 h between 23 h and 7 h. L_{den} noise indicator is defined as shown in Eq. 1:

$$172 \quad L_{den} = 10 \cdot \lg \frac{1}{24} \left(12 \cdot 10^{\frac{L_d}{10}} + 4 \cdot 10^{\frac{L_e+5}{10}} + 8 \cdot 10^{\frac{L_n+10}{10}} \right), \quad (1)$$

173 Each station started measuring at different times: at point 1, measurements started on 1 February; at point
174 2, they started on 10 February; and at point 3, on 1 March. The measuring stations operated continuously
175 during the study period, except when stations 2 and 3 were inoperative for a few days due to technical
176 problems. Specifically, station 2 had problems between 30 May and 2 June, and station 3 had problems
177 between 30 April and 4 June.

178 It is necessary to bear in mind that road traffic is the main source of noise in cities worldwide
179 (European Environment Agency 2020). In the case of the city of Cáceres, road traffic is also the main source
180 of variability in the recorded sound levels, as shown in previous studies (Barrigón Morillas et al. 2002;
181 Barrigón Morillas et al. 2005a; Barrigón Morillas et al. 2005b; Rey Gozalo et al. 2019b). These works
182 demonstrate how solely the number of vehicles passing by the sound level meter (without considering the

183 type of vehicle, its age, speed, or specific characteristics of the street or its geometric configuration) can
184 account for 85% of the variability in the registered equivalent sound pressure level in different types of
185 urban roads, and how the estimated noise levels in the road traffic noise map of the city have low uncertainty
186 compared to in-situ sound measurements. However, traffic volume data are not always available in cities
187 or they are not as comprehensive as desired. For the present work, data were provided by Cáceres City
188 Council (private communication) on the number of vehicles that were in circulation, on a month-by-month
189 basis, between January 2019 to June 2020. Only 10 streets had sensors to determine traffic volume per
190 month. These streets were classified as Category 1 (five streets), Category 2 (three streets) and Category 3
191 (two streets) (Barrigón Morillas et al. 2002; 2005a). None of the streets where urban noise measurements
192 were conducted had a traffic volume sensor. A model of the urban environment of point 1 was performed
193 with Predictor v11.20 software for environmental noise. From the monthly average vehicle flow data of
194 category 3 streets, the noise level values were estimated in point 1 using NMPB-Routes-96 method (NMPB-
195 Routes-96/XPS 31–133). Tool 3.5 and Tool 4.5 of the Good Practice Guide for Strategic Noise Mapping
196 (WG-AEN 2007) were used to estimate the percentage of heavy vehicles and vehicle speed. This model
197 provides an approximation of the variation in the L_d indicator that could be awaited with the expected
198 decrease in flow on the street where point 1 is located if the traffic flow behaviour is similar to that of
199 category 3 streets for which traffic volume data is available. Since traffic volume data was not available for
200 any Category 4 and 5 streets (which are the type of streets where points 2 and 3 are located), it was not
201 possible to model the environmental noise for points 2 and 3.

202 Since road traffic is considered the main source of mobility in cities (Mattioli et al. 2020), a
203 parameter that quantifies this mobility could be used as an alternative to traffic flow. In this sense, mobility
204 data provided by the Secretary of State for Transport, Mobility and the Urban Agenda (2022) were also
205 considered. A study carried out by the Ministry for Transport, Mobility and the Urban Agenda aimed to
206 characterise daily vehicle mobility in the country, in order to assess the effectiveness of the measures
207 adopted to restrict this mobility and to support decision-making during the pandemic. As explained on their
208 website, this analysis used the positioning of mobile phones as its main source of data, in compliance with
209 current regulations on personal data protection. This information was complemented by data on land use
210 and information on the transport network. A comparison of mobility was carried out with the period from
211 14 to 20 February 2020.

212 Just like road traffic is the main source of noise, it is also one of the primary sources of atmospheric
213 pollution related to NO_x (around 35 % of NO_x EU emissions are attributed to road transport), although this
214 is not the case for PM_{10} (around 10 %) (European Environment Agency 2023). Therefore, the previous
215 hypothesis, which suggested the existence of a relationship between mobility and sound levels, was also
216 proposed for the air pollutants PM_{10} and NO_2 . Thus, daily air concentration data for PM_{10} and NO_2 provided
217 by the General Office for the Environment of the Regional Government of Extremadura (private
218 communication) were taken into account in this study. These data were measured at the only suburban air
219 quality monitoring station in the city, as shown in Fig.1b. This station forms part of the Air Quality
220 Monitoring Network of Extremadura. The data were collected using methods set out in the standard
221 protocols established by the European Union's air quality monitoring networks, and equipment were
222 routinely calibrated and maintained based on these standards. The location of the station in relation to the
223 noise level measurement points can be seen in Fig. 1b. During certain periods, the station was unable to
224 correctly assess the presence of PM_{10} ; the intervals for which no PM_{10} data were available were from
225 2020/4/3 to 2020/4/16, from 2020/5/5 to 2020/5/7, from 2020/5/15 to 2020/5/20 and from 2020/6/5 to
226 2020/6/23.

227 In this study, daily data of meteorological variables such as average temperature, precipitation
228 volume, wind speed, and hours of sunshine (AEMET OpenData 2023) were also available, which could
229 also show a notable relationship with mobility or atmospheric pollutants.

230 A Spearman's rank correlation test was employed to assess the degree of association between
231 mobility and atmospheric pollutants (chemicals and noise) using the `cor.test` function in R software version
232 4.3.1 (refer to Tables 7 and 8 in Appendix A). This non-parametric test was chosen due to the variables not
233 meeting the assumptions of normality (Shapiro-Wilk test), homoscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan test), and
234 linearity (RESET test) (Hollander et al. 2014). Meteorological variables (temperature, wind speed,

235 precipitation, sunshine hours) could potentially act as confounding variables, meaning variables that exhibit
 236 a significant association with atmospheric pollutants (chemicals and noise). Therefore, if this is the case,
 237 Tables 7 and 8 in Appendix A do not represent the specific portion of variance explained by the mobility
 238 variable (Stevens 2002).

239 Regarding the relationship between sound and meteorological variables, considering the proximity
 240 between the sound source and receiver, the influence of meteorological variables on sound propagation
 241 should be minimal, as indicated by the calculations in ISO 9613-2. A correlation analysis between
 242 atmospheric pollutants and meteorological variables was performed using the Spearman's rank test, and the
 243 results are presented in Tables 9 and 10 in Appendix B. Based on the findings shown in Tables 9 and 10
 244 (Appendix B), the effects of meteorological variables that exhibited a significant association with
 245 atmospheric pollutants were removed to express the true level of association (the specific part of variance
 246 explained by the mobility variable) between mobility and atmospheric pollutants. Partial Spearman
 247 correlations using the ppcor package in R software were used to control for potential effects of
 248 meteorological variables (Kim 2015). Furthermore, the confidence interval of the partial correlations was
 249 calculated using the RVAideMemoire package in R software.

250

251 **Results**

252 **Noise indicators**

253

254 Fig. 2 shows the daily values obtained for L_d , L_e and L_n at the three measurement points. Vertical lines
 255 indicate the different stages of the lockdown. The acoustic quality objectives for noise in sectors with
 256 predominantly residential land use, according to the Spanish government (*Real Decreto* 1367 2007), are
 257 marked horizontally. These values are 65 dB for L_d and L_e , and 55 dB for L_n (black horizontal lines). The
 258 strong recommendation of the WHO (2018) for road traffic noise, whereby the value of L_n should be below
 259 45 dB, is also indicated with a red horizontal line.

260

261 (a)

262

263 (b)

264

265 (c)

266

267 **Fig. 2** Variation in the sound indicators L_d , L_e and L_n over the period considered: (a) point 1; (b) point 2;
 268 (c) point 3.

269

270 Table 11 in appendix C show the mean values of the noise indicators L_d , L_e and L_n along with the
 271 standard error of the mean for the different stages considered. A noteworthy drop in the L_d and L_n levels
 272 during stages B, C, D and E (representing the most severe restrictions due to the state of emergency) can
 273 be seen from Fig. 2, although these are not as prominent for L_e . For L_d on weekdays, there is initially a drop
 274 of almost 3.5 dB at point 1 (Fig. 2a and Table 11 in Appendix C) during stage B with respect to stage A,
 275 and this difference reaches more than 5 dB in stage C (with stricter limitations on movements). This drop
 276 is reduced as time progresses, and the values during stages I and J are only slightly lower than in stage A,
 277 with a reduction of a little more than 1 dB. The particularly high values during stage F were due to road
 278 works. At point 2 (Fig. 2b and Table 11 in Appendix C), there is a drop of about 3 dB during stages B, C,
 279 D, E and F compared to stage A. This reduction is lessened in the following stages; in the last two stages (I
 280 and J) the difference is maintained and is slightly less than 2 dB. At point 3 (Fig. 2c and Table 11 in
 281 Appendix C), the drop is more moderate (about 2 dB in stages B and C with respect to stage A), and from
 282 stage D onwards, levels similar to those pre-COVID-19 are reached again. It can also be seen that in the
 283 last two stages, the levels at this point are similar to those of stage A.

284 In the case of L_e , the drops are more moderate, and it can even be seen that the values are higher
285 than in the pre-COVID-19 period at points 2 and 3. This is due to some specific situations that occurred
286 during the period under study: (a) there was applause on balconies and windows for health personnel
287 throughout this period, from the first day of the state of emergency, at 8:00 pm, and (b) there were protests
288 against the measures taken by the Spanish government with pots and pans, which occurred from the
289 beginning of April at 9:00 pm. In addition, parades were held on some days with ambulances, police cars
290 and music, to cheer up the children forced to stay at home during the lockdown. These noisy activities
291 produced higher L_e values than before the pandemic, but decreased as the anti-COVID-19 measures were
292 relaxed, with values returning in stage J to levels similar to those before the declaration of the state of
293 emergency (stage A).

294 The most **important** drop in L_n on weekdays occurs at point 1, in stages B, C, D and E, with values
295 of between 5 and 6 dB with respect to stage A. Again, the values rise throughout the period under study. In
296 the last stages for all three points, an increase of almost 1 dB is seen compared to the pre-pandemic levels;
297 this was primarily due to the arrival of warmer weather and the widespread use of bar terraces, since it was
298 permitted to be outside in these establishments. It should be noted that in Cáceres, evenings and nights are
299 cool in March, with temperatures of between 6.7 °C and 17.7 °C (*Agencia Estatal de Meteorología* 2023),
300 and it is not normal practice to be outside on bar terraces, whereas temperatures are higher in June, and are
301 between 16.0 °C and 29.9 °C (*Agencia Estatal de Meteorología* 2023).

302 For the three noise indicators, a **considerable** reduction can be seen at some days of the weekends
303 in stages B, C, D and E (the most restrictive state of emergency), with values of between 5 dB and 9 dB in
304 relation to some weekend days of the pre-COVID-19 stage (stage A). For some weekend nights during the
305 state of emergency, there was even a drop of more than 10 dB relative to the pre-COVID-19 period. At
306 weekends, average drops in L_d of between 3 and 5 dB are observed at points 1 and 2, but there is almost no
307 reduction in L_d at point 3. The comparison with L_e is distorted by the balcony noise mentioned above, which
308 continued at weekends. The largest drops can be seen at night, with average decreases in L_n of about 8 dB
309 at point 1 and about 5 dB at points 2 and 3 in stages B, C, D and E.

310 Regarding the acoustic quality objectives (*Real Decreto* 1367 2007) of the Spanish government,
311 it can be seen from Fig. 2 that these objectives had already been achieved before the pandemic at the three
312 points of interest. It can also be observed that as the restrictions were lifted and the weather conditions
313 improved, the L_n quality objectives were exceeded during weekends, which was less often the case in the
314 period prior to the declaration of the state of emergency.

315 If the value recommended by the WHO for L_n is considered, it can be seen that it was usually
316 exceeded at all three points. Values below this level were only achieved on some Sundays and public
317 holidays during the most severe period of lockdown, and this recommended threshold was largely exceeded
318 as the restrictions were reduced and good weather arrived.

319 Although the Spanish government does not set acoustic quality objectives for L_{den} , it is noted that
320 this noise indicator, together with L_n , is preferred for strategic noise maps. Having established quality
321 objectives for L_d , L_e and L_n , a value for the L_{den} indicator can be obtained from its definition (Eq. 1), where
322 $L_d = 65$ dB, $L_e = 65$ dB and $L_n = 55$ dB. This gives a value of $L_{den} = 66.3$ dB. The WHO (2018) also sets a
323 threshold for road traffic noise (the predominant sound source throughout the day in the urban environments
324 evaluated here) and strongly recommends that this does not exceed a value of $L_{den} = 53$ dB. The results
325 obtained for the three points in the different stages considered here are shown in Fig. 3. The quality
326 objective set by the Spanish government is shown with a black horizontal line, and the WHO value with a
327 red horizontal line. It can be seen from Fig. 3 that the acoustic quality objectives of the Spanish government
328 are always met at all three points, but that the WHO recommendations for L_{den} are exceeded. The measured
329 values were close to the recommended limit on only two days at point 2, corresponding to two particularly
330 quiet Sundays in stage F.

331

332

333 **Fig. 3** Variation in the noise indicator L_{den} during the period considered at the three measurement points.

334

335 The L_e values measured during the lockdown period do not correspond to the levels that would be
 336 expected under normal conditions, meaning that the calculated L_{den} values are also affected by this problem.
 337 To address this issue, three possibilities were considered for estimating L_e . The first (*estimate 1*) involved
 338 calculating the mean difference between L_d and L_e during the pre-pandemic period and taking $L_{e_estimated}$ as
 339 the L_d value for a given day minus the mean difference between L_d and L_e . Another possibility (*estimate 2*)
 340 involved calculating the average difference between L_e and L_n during the pre-pandemic period, and taking
 341 $L_{e_estimated}$ as the value of L_n on a given day plus the mean difference between L_e and L_n . Finally, as a lower
 342 limit on $L_{e_estimated}$, the value of L_n for that day was taken (*estimate 3*). To check the accuracy of these L_{den}
 343 estimates, they were compared with the actual values measured on the days prior to the declaration of the
 344 state of alarm. The results of this comparison can be seen in Fig. 8 and Table 12 in Appendix D. When
 345 "Estimate 1" is indicated in Fig. 8 (Appendix D), it shows the result of subtracting "estimate 1" from the
 346 real L_{den} value. Similarly, "Estimate 2" reflects the result of subtracting "estimate 2" from the actual L_{den}
 347 value, and "Estimate 3" indicates the result of subtracting "estimate 3" from the actual L_{den} value. In Fig. 8
 348 (Appendix D), it can be observed that the majority of differences for "estimate 1" and "estimate 2" are
 349 between [-0.5 dB, +0.5 dB]: 84.2 % and 76.3 %, respectively, for point 1; 87.9 % and 63.6 %, for point 2,
 350 and 100 % and 76.9 % for point 3. In the case of "estimate 3," most of the time, the difference is 1 dB or
 351 more (89.5 % for point 1; 97.0 % for point 2, and 15.4 % for point 3), and it is positive on all points and all
 352 days; that is, the values of L_{den} obtained based on the approximation $L_e = L_n$ impose a lower limit on L_{den} .
 353 Some statistical parameters for the differences between the real values of L_{den} during stage A and the
 354 different estimates considered for the three points are shown in Table 12 (Appendix D). It can be seen that
 355 *estimate 1* is slightly better than *estimate 2*. Furthermore, *estimate 3* represents a lower bound of the real
 356 value, as mentioned before. One can conclude that the estimates of L_e based on the mean differences
 357 between L_d and L_e or the mean differences between L_e and L_n are acceptable, in view of the closeness
 358 between the measured and estimated values.

359 Using these three estimates of L_e , the values of L_{den} were recalculated, and the results are shown
 360 in Fig. 4. The horizontal blue line indicates the maximum value of L_{den} recommended by the WHO. At
 361 point 1, values below the WHO recommendation were not achieved on any day, even with the
 362 approximation $L_e = L_n$. At points 2 and 3, values lower than those recommended by the WHO may have
 363 been achieved on some days, but these were Sundays or public holidays, and never working days. In view
 364 of the results of this study, it can be concluded that reaching the WHO's recommended values for L_{den} is
 365 very difficult in urban environments, even under conditions of extreme reductions in traffic.

366

367

368

369

(c)

370 **Fig. 4** L_{den} values considering different estimates for L_e at: (a) point 1; (b) point 2; (c) point 3.

371

372 **Mobility**

373 As mentioned above, the economic sector related to services was the most affected by the lockdown. And
 374 within this sector, the one related to tourism experienced a complete halt. Likewise, the number of overnight
 375 stays dropped precipitously, as shown in Table 2 (Cáceres City Council, private communication); in other
 376 words, the number of visitors and hence the vehicular traffic arising from these visits decreased noticeably.
 377 This number of overnight stays is another indicator of the variation in economic activity in the city, where,
 378 as mentioned in the Introduction, there was a 9 % decrease in per capita GDP in 2020 compared to the per
 379 capita GDP in 2019. As stated above, this economic halt is evident due to the mandated closure of nearly
 380 all direct customer-facing businesses and restrictions on public movement without a valid reason during
 381 the lockdown imposed by the Spanish government (Table 1).

382

383 **Table 2** Number of overnight stays in Cáceres during 2019 and 2020 in the period under study

Year	Overnight stays				
	February	March	April	May	June
2019	16,939	25,993	53,279	38,325	24,376
2020	17,456	4,835	0	0	1,147

384

385 Fig. 5 shows the average volume of vehicles per month in different streets of the city, based on
 386 data provided by the traffic sensors and distributed by Cáceres City Council. The monthly values for
 387 February, March, April, May and June are compared for 2019 and 2020. A drop of 51 % in the overall
 388 traffic in the city was observed during the months of March and April, with reductions of 59 % in May and
 389 32 % in June. If only Category 3 streets, for which there are traffic values, are considered, the reductions
 390 were 75 % in March, 76 % in April, 87 % in May and 18 % in June. The acoustic levels in Cáceres were
 391 extensively studied during 2002 (Barrigón Morillas et al. 2002), 2005 (Barrigón Morillas et al. 2005a) and
 392 2019 (Rey Gozalo et al. 2019b). In each of these studies, a statistically significant correlation between
 393 traffic flow (Q) and measured equivalent noise level (L_{eq}) was verified.

394

Using the results from the software model describe above, a comparison between the average decrease in traffic noise due to traffic flow variation between the years 2019 and 2020 on Category 3 streets

396 and the L_d noise indicator decrease at point 1, also located in Category 3, is shown in Table 3. Since no
 397 measured acoustic data are available for 2019, the average value of the L_d noise indicator from 1 to 13
 398 March 2020 is taken as the base value. It can be seen that the software model predictions for March, April
 399 and June are fairly accurate, with variations of about 1.5 dB, as can be seen in the fifth column of Table 3.
 400 The highest variation for Q_{2020}/Q_{2019} occurs in May (0.13 in the second column of Table 3), due to the
 401 reduction in the number of vehicles circulating during this month. This can be explained due to the
 402 improvement in the weather compared to April (mean temperatures 5 °C higher in May; 9 rainy days in
 403 May compared to 19 in April; *Agencia Estatal de Meteorología* 2020) and the easing of the restrictions on
 404 mobility, which encouraged citizens to travel on foot instead of by car. The difference between the software
 405 model and the estimated variation for point 1 for May (5.5 dB) might be due to the fact that road works
 406 were being carried out in the central area of the avenue, which did not interrupt traffic but increased the
 407 measured L_d levels. The differences of around 1.5 dB for the other months can be considered acceptable
 408 since there is no disaggregated data available on the vehicles circulating on the avenue (point 1).

409

410

411 **Fig. 5** Monthly average number of vehicles circulating on the main roads of Cáceres.

412

413 **Table 3** Comparison between the variation expected in road traffic noise due to the change in traffic volume
 414 (Q) in Category 3 streets and at point 1 ($L_{d,SA}$ corresponds to the mean L_d value from 1 to 13 March, stage
 415 A; $L_{d,month}$ is the mean L_d value for each month)

Month	Q_{2020}/Q_{2019} (Category 3)	$L_d 2020 - L_d 2019$ (Software Model) (dB)	$L_{d,month} - L_{d,SA}$ (Point 1) (dB)	Difference Point 1 – Software Model (dB)
March	0.25	-6.0	-4.4 ^a	1.6
April	0.24	-6.1	-4.5	1.6
May	0.13	-9.4	-3.9	5.5
June	0.82	-3.4	-1.9	1.5

416 ^aThe days from the declaration of the state of emergency (14 March) to the end of the month are considered
 417 for $L_{d,month}$.

418

419 As mentioned above, the variation in mobility within the city of Cáceres according to the study
 420 carried out by the Secretary of State for Transport, Mobility and Urban Agenda was also considered. Fig.
 421 6 shows the percentage change in mobility in Cáceres, in relation to the reference period (from 14 to 20

422 February 2020). The published data start on 29 February 2020. There is clearly a sharp drop in mobility at
 423 the beginning of the state of emergency (stage B), which reaches a minimum in stage C (when only workers
 424 in key economic sectors were allowed to move about). Gradually, as the measures were relaxed, mobility
 425 increased until it reached values similar to those before the pandemic (stage J). The results of the Spearman's
 426 rank correlation test on the degree of association between % mobility and noise indicators are shown in
 427 Appendix A, Table 7. It can be seen that at each of the three points, there is a **statistically significant**
 428 correlation between the measured values of the daily sound levels L_d and L_n and the percentage variation of
 429 mobility in the city. For point 1, this **statistically very highly significant** ($p < 0.001$) correlation also holds
 430 for L_e and L_{den} . For point 2 and 3 L_{den} , the value of Spearman's rho indicates that the correlation is between
 431 **highly significant** ($p < 0.01$) and **significant** ($p < 0.05$), while it is **very highly significant** ($p < 0.001$) for
 432 point 1. This may indicate that the overall variation in mobility in the city affects main streets (as streets in
 433 Category 3) more than neighbourhood streets (Categories 4 and 5).
 434

435
 436 **Fig. 6** Percentage change in daily mobility in vehicles in the city of Cáceres within the reference period
 437 established by the Secretary of State (from February 14 to 20, 2020).
 438

439 **Air pollution**

440
 441 The daily air concentration data for PM_{10} and NO_2 provided by the General Office for the Environment of
 442 the Regional Government of Extremadura for the period studied in the present work were analysed. Table
 443 13 in Appendix E shows the values established by the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic
 444 Challenge of the Spanish government for air quality (2020), and Table 14 in Appendix E shows the WHO's
 445 recommendations (2021).

446 The daily variation in the air pollutants PM_{10} and NO_2 , together with L_{den} for point 1, can be seen
 447 in Fig. 7. Table 4 shows the average variation in these parameters over the different periods considered.
 448 The values for the air pollutants and L_{den} are shown together, in view of their possible dependence on road
 449 traffic in the cities. This dependence is shown in Table 7 (Appendix A) for L_{den} , and can be seen in Table 8
 450 (Appendix A) for PM_{10} and NO_2 . A decrease in NO_2 from stage B onwards is shown in Table 4; the level
 451 subsequently increases, although pre-pandemic values are not reached. There is also a drop in PM_{10} in stage
 452 B, and the value reaches a minimum in stage C. From this period onwards, PM_{10} levels increase faster than
 453 NO_2 levels, and reach values higher than in the pre-pandemic period in stages H, I and J. Similar results
 454 have been reported by other authors (Tobías et al. 2020). In terms of the categories defined in Spanish
 455 legislation, the levels of PM_{10} and NO_2 correspond to good air quality. For PM_{10} , the annual limits
 456 established by the WHO were slightly exceeded in stages H and J, and in stage I, the value was within the

457 established limit. For NO₂, the WHO annual limits were not exceeded in any of the periods. When the daily
 458 values are considered, it was observed that there was no day where the limit established by the WHO was
 459 exceeded for 24 h, either for PM₁₀ or NO₂. L_{den} undergoes a drop in stage B, as already mentioned, reaching
 460 a minimum in stage C. From this stage onwards, L_{den} values start to rise, reaching levels similar to the pre-
 461 pandemic period in stages I and J.

462

463

464 **Fig. 7** Variation in air pollutants NO₂ and PM₁₀ with values of L_{den} for point 1 during the different stages
 465 of the lockdown.

466

467 **Table 4** Average values of L_{den} (at point 1), NO₂ and PM₁₀ during the different stages of the lockdown

Stage	Length	L_{den} (point 1) (dB)	PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	NO ₂ (µg/m ³)
A	2020/02/01 – 2020/03/13	63.3	13.4	9.6
B	2020/03/14 – 2020/03/29	59.2	9.1	2.2
C	2020/03/30 – 2020/04/09	58.1	3.2	2.4
D	2020/04/10 – 2020/04/25	59.5	7.1	1.9
E	2020/04/26 – 2020/04/03	58.7	7.1	2.0
F	2020/05/04 – 2020/05/10	58.5	12.5	2.2
G	2020/05/11 – 2020/05/24	61.1	10.7	2.8
H	2020/05/25 – 2020/06/07	62.0	18.0	3.1
I	2020/06/08 – 2020/06/21	63.1	15.0	3.5
J	2020/06/22 – 2020/06/30	63.1	15.2	4.3

468

469 As mentioned above, the results of the Spearman's rank correlation test for the degree of
 470 association between % mobility change and chemical pollutants PM₁₀ and NO₂ are shown in Appendix A,
 471 Table 8. It can be seen that this correlation is statistically very significant in both cases. In the case of NO₂,
 472 this correlation is moderate, while for PM₁₀, it is weak. This result for PM₁₀ is in line with previous findings

473 reported by other authors (Pivato et al. 2023), and is due to the influence of other factors on the level of
 474 PM₁₀, such as domestic heating systems, agricultural activities, and livestock farms.

475

476 **Influence of meteorological variables**

477 Regarding the possible influence of meteorological variables on the previously shown results, the
 478 Spearman's rank correlation test was also applied. The results shown in Table 9 (Appendix B) confirm the
 479 low relationship between meteorological variables and noise indicators. In general, there are not many
 480 significant relationships, and when they exist, the rho value indicates a low degree of association. Regarding
 481 the relationship between noise indicators and precipitation, significant relationships between noise level
 482 and precipitation are only observed in point 1 for all periods (L_d , L_e , L_n , and L_{den}), while in points 2 and 3,
 483 it occurs in only one period, and it is not the same in both cases. In all cases where significant relationships
 484 occur, the coefficient is negative and ranges from -0.241 to -0.382. In other words, as precipitation
 485 increases, the noise level decreases. This could be related to various factors such as variations in tire-
 486 pavement noise generation due to changes in asphalt properties when wet, or variations in vehicle traffic
 487 conditions in terms of speed for visibility and safety reasons.

488 In the case of Table 10 (Appendix B), there is a higher degree of association between
 489 meteorological variables and atmospheric chemical pollutants as see for other authors (Huang et al. 2021;
 490 Pearce et al. 2011). A significant positive relationship is observed between PM₁₀ concentration and
 491 temperature and the number of hours of sunshine. As for wind speed, this meteorological variable only
 492 shows a significant negative relationship with NO₂ concentration. Regarding precipitation, both for NO₂
 493 and PM₁₀ concentration, a significant negative relationship is obtained with association coefficients ranging
 494 between -0.414 and -0.471.

495 Considering the influence of a third group of variables (meteorological variables) on the
 496 relationship between noise indicators and chemical pollutants with respect to % mobility change, a partial
 497 correlation analysis was conducted. This way, the potential influence of meteorological variables was
 498 removed when testing the hypothesis of the relationship between noise indicators, chemical pollutants, and
 499 % mobility change. Results are shown in Tables 5 and 6. If Table 5 is considered and compared to the
 500 results shown in Table 7 (Appendix A), it can be seen that the same statistically significant relationships
 501 are maintained (except for the statistically significant relationship for L_{den} in point 3) and the degrees of
 502 association are also almost the same. It can be concluded that the relationship between noise indicators and
 503 the % mobility is not affected by meteorological variables. It can be seen that the correlation between L_e
 504 and % mobility change in point 3 is negative. As explained in the subsection "Noise Indicators" of the
 505 Results, the values of L_e (and, consequently, L_{den}) are affected by the events that occurred in the evenings
 506 on the balconies during the pandemic, with noisy demonstrations (applause, music, pot-banging) in support
 507 of healthcare workers or against the anti-pandemic measures implemented by the government. Due to these
 508 circumstances and the characteristics regarding the intensity of these sound sources on the balconies, road
 509 traffic may not have been the predominant sound source during that time of day. Consequently, the results
 510 in L_e and L_{den} could have been influenced by these non-daily, unusual sound sources in a normal urban
 511 environment. One possible explanation is that reduced mobility results in more people staying at home, and
 512 consequently, more noise on balconies. Nevertheless, this correlation, although statistically significant,
 513 should be interpreted with caution. Comparing Table 6 with Table 8 (Appendix A), it can be observed that
 514 it remains almost the same for the case of NO₂ concentration, but the correlation disappears for PM₁₀,
 515 indicating that the relationship between this chemical pollutant and the % mobility change is much weaker,
 516 as mentioned before.

517

518 **Table 5** Spearman's rank partial correlation between the noise indices (L_d , L_e , L_n , L_{den}) and % mobility
 519 change

Point 1				Point 2				Point 3			
L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}	L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}	L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}

rho	0.766	0.594	0.708	0.748	0.663	-0.014	0.668	0.348	0.430	-0.395	0.330	0.099
Upper 95% C.I.	0.845	0.723	0.798	0.828	0.779	0.176	0.775	0.520	0.587	-0.204	0.534	0.335
Lower 95% C.I.	0.658	0.438	0.581	0.653	0.518	-0.207	0.528	0.160	0.243	-0.555	0.090	-0.151
<i>p</i> value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	n.s.	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.01	n.s.
<i>N</i>	116	123	123	116	120	119	120	119	87	86	86	85

520 n.s.: Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$)

521 C.I.: Confidence interval

522

523 **Table 6** Spearman's rank partial correlation between PM₁₀, NO₂ and % mobility change.

	PM ₁₀	NO ₂
rho	0.181	0.706
Upper 95% C.I.	0.417	0.792
Lower 95% C.I.	-0.038	0.592
<i>p</i> value	n.s.	<0.001
<i>N</i>	80	123

525 n.s.: Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$)

526 C.I.: Confidence interval

527

528 Discussion

529

530 As discussed in the Introduction, the WHO recommends changes in infrastructure to reduce the adverse
531 health effects associated with high levels of noise. This recommendation ties in with SDGs 3 and 11
532 established by the UN for 2030, and more specifically with targets 3.9 (*By 2030, substantially reduce the*
533 *number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and*
534 *contamination*) and 11.6 (*By 2030, reduce the adverse per capita environmental impact of cities*). However,
535 the data presented in this paper indicate that these are still far from being achieved.

536 Before discussing the findings, it would be interesting to highlight that the WHO recommendations
537 are for traffic noise, but the noise indicators shown in the previous section reflect the environmental noise
538 around the measurement point, not just the traffic noise. However, the categorization method developed by
539 Barrigón Morillas et al. (2005a, 2005b) demonstrates that the noise level in city streets is stratified based
540 on established categories determined by the road traffic use of these streets. Furthermore, it also
541 demonstrates that urban noise is strongly correlated with traffic flow, which is the primary source of spatial
542 variation in urban noise. Therefore, the city's noise is strongly linked to traffic flow, which is the main
543 source of spatial variation in urban noise. In this regard, when there has been excessive noise in the evenings
544 due to activities on balconies, it has been noted, and an estimation of what the L_e noise indicator value could
545 have been without those activities has been considered, as explained later in this section.

546 From Eq. 1 and the WHO's recommendations for L_{den} (53 dB) and L_n (45 dB), an estimate of
547 possible recommended values for L_d and L_e can be made. The range for L_d is between 50 dB and 52 dB,
548 while the range for L_e is between 50 dB and 45 dB. If equal values for L_d and L_e are considered (as set out
549 by the Spanish government), then $L_d = L_e = 50$ dB. However, if equal values for L_e and L_n are considered
550 (with a high requirement for L_e), then $L_d = 52$ dB and $L_e = 45$ dB. Fig. 2 shows that at point 1, both L_d and
551 L_e are rarely lower than 55 dB; they never fall below this value in the pre-pandemic period, and only
552 occasionally during the most restrictive times of the pandemic. In stage A (pre-pandemic) and stage J (end
553 of mobility restrictions), values between 60 and 65 dB are observed for L_d and L_e , with L_d usually higher
554 and L_e lower. At point 2, L_d reached values below or close to 50 dB on Sundays during the most stringent

555 stage of lockdown (stage C), while on the other days, it was above 55 dB. Again, at point 2, the values of
556 L_e were always above 55 dB; this demonstrates the effect that noisy events seem to have on noise indicators,
557 which in many cases are used as indicators in strategic noise maps to make decisions about the acoustic
558 situation in a given area (Montes González et al. 2023; Prieto Gajardo et al. 2014). At point 2, L_d was around
559 60 dB in stage A, and L_e was around 58 dB, while in stage J, both indicators were around 58 dB. At point
560 3, L_d did not reach values lower than 54 dB, and values of around 54 dB were achieved only on some
561 Sundays in stages B and C. L_e had values of above 55 dB, except on some Sundays, where values fell to
562 around 54 dB. In stages A and J, the values of L_d and L_e ranged between 55 dB and 60 dB. It can therefore
563 be seen that the values strongly recommended by the WHO were difficult (if not impossible) to achieve,
564 even on residential streets in a small-to-medium-sized city, during a period of time when economic activity
565 was almost at a standstill.

566 Using the software model for Virgen de la Montaña Avenue (point 1), an estimate can be made of
567 what the vehicle flow should be to achieve the values recommended by the WHO for L_{den} (53 dB) and L_n
568 (45 dB). In the case of L_{den} , a value of 53 dB would be obtained with an average monthly vehicle **volume**
569 of 14,000 vehicles/month. This **volume** would result in an L_n value of 43.3 dB, thus meeting both
570 recommendations. If the goal is to ensure an L_n value of 45 dB, it could be achieved with a monthly vehicle
571 **volume** of 20,000 vehicles/month, although in this case, an L_{den} value of 53.8 dB would be obtained, which
572 is higher than the WHO's recommended value. The average number of vehicles on Category 3 streets
573 measured between March and June 2019 was 114,639 vehicles. Therefore, according to the software model,
574 this represents a reduction in vehicle **volume** of 88% in the first case and 82% in the second case. Taking
575 into account the actual average reduction during the lockdown, the **traffic volume** decreased by 64%
576 compared to the vehicle **volume** values of 2019. In other words, a further 20% reduction in vehicle **volume**
577 would be needed compared to the lockdown period to achieve the values recommended by the WHO for
578 the noise indicators L_{den} and L_n .

579 It can therefore be concluded that achieving the values strongly recommended by the WHO for
580 the noise indicators in a city would require a drastic reduction in road traffic flow. Furthermore, electric
581 vehicles are not expected to provide a solution, as several studies (Rey-Gozalo et al. 2022; Leupolz &
582 Gauterin 2022; Altinsoy 2022) show that little change can be expected at current vehicle speeds in cities
583 (generally above 30 km/h) unless this is accompanied by other, more effective measures, such as better
584 road surfaces. However, these solutions may impose higher costs on the public treasury or even create a
585 higher carbon footprint.

586 In regard to air pollution from internal combustion vehicles, better results might be possible, at
587 least in the case of NO_2 concentration, if traffic circulation is reduced or the use of electric vehicles is
588 increased, as shown in Fig. 6 and Table 7. Other authors (Muhammad et al. 2020; Nakada & Urban 2020)
589 have published similar results. A reduction in air pollution in cities around the world has been observed
590 experimentally when the circulation of internal combustion vehicles has been reduced. Replacing internal
591 combustion vehicles with electric vehicles would improve air quality in cities; however, this electricity
592 needs to come from sources that generate minimal carbon emissions, as otherwise, the problem is simply
593 being moved elsewhere. Initiatives such as the European Commission's Lightyear Project (2020) for solar-
594 powered self-driving cars have achieved promising results.

595

596 **Conclusions**

597

598 This study has analysed air and noise pollution in the city of Cáceres during the period from March to June
599 2020, during which Spain underwent an abrupt halt in economic activity due to the measures taken by the
600 Spanish government to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic. Data for the period prior to the declaration of the
601 state of emergency in Spain (14 March 2020) were used as a reference to establish pre-pandemic noise and
602 air pollution levels. The variations in these levels in the city were examined in the different phases of the
603 lockdown, from almost total immobility to the return to a "new normal" at the end of June. As the city's
604 main economic activity is oriented towards the service sector and tourism, the reduction in the use of private

605 vehicles fell to levels that had never been seen before. These conditions made it possible to analyse the
606 variation in noise levels and air pollution in three streets in the city.

607 In terms of noise levels, the most **important** drop was seen in Virgen de la Montaña Avenue (point
608 1), a wide street with one lane in each direction, parking on both sides and a wide, landscaped central
609 promenade. There was a decrease of more than 5 dB in the L_d value during the most restrictive period of
610 the lockdown. In Gredos Street (point 2), a road with one lane of traffic in each direction and parking on
611 both sides, the value of L_d decreased by about 3 dB. In Dr. Fleming Street (point 3), which has one-way
612 traffic and parking on both sides, the drop in noise levels was not as sharp, with a decrease of about 2 dB
613 in L_d .

614 The noise quality objectives set by the Spanish government had already been achieved before the
615 pandemic. However, this was not the case for the objectives set by the WHO; the recommendations for L_{den}
616 and L_n were rarely reached, and this occurred only on Sundays or public holidays during the strictest period
617 of lockdown.

618 The reduction in air pollution was **notable** for NO_2 , and apparently for PM_{10} , during the period of
619 strict lockdown. NO_2 values remained relatively low throughout the period under study, and this decrease
620 was correlated with the decrease in the % mobility change. For PM_{10} , although there was a decrease in its
621 concentration during the strict confinement, no correlation has been found with the % mobility change once
622 the potential influence of meteorological variables has been eliminated.

623 The reduction in the use of private vehicles led to improvements in both air quality and noise
624 levels. However, in the case of noise pollution, this improvement was not sufficient to achieve the noise
625 quality objectives based on the indicators proposed by the WHO. Our results show that although replacing
626 internal combustion vehicles by electric vehicles would lead to a certain improvement in air quality, the
627 levels would still be well above the WHO recommendations for both L_{den} and L_n . It can be therefore
628 conclude that in medium-sized cities such as Cáceres, a much more drastic reduction in traffic flow would
629 be necessary to achieve compliance with the values established by the WHO for noise levels, as these are
630 well below the minimum values that were obtained with the mobility restrictions imposed by the Spanish
631 government to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic.

632

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636

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642

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649

650 **Availability of data and materials** The datasets used or analysed to support the findings of this study
651 are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

652

653

654 **Declarations**

655

656 **Ethics approval and consent to participate** Not applicable.

657

658 **Consent for publication** Not applicable.

659

660 **Competing interests** The authors declare no competing interests.

661

662 **Appendix A**

663 Results of the Spearman's rank correlation test on the degree of association between % mobility change and
664 noise indicators and between % mobility change and chemical pollutants PM₁₀ and NO₂.

665

666 **Table 7** Relationship between the noise indicators (L_d , L_e , L_n , L_{den}) and % mobility change.

	Point 1				Point 2				Point 3			
	L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}	L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}	L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}
Spearman's rho	0.766	0.620	0.756	0.771	0.663	-0.121	0.715	0.295	0.430	-0.395	0.431	0.224
p value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	n.s.	<0.001	<0.01	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.05

667 n.s.: Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$)

668

669 **Table 8** Relationship between PM₁₀, NO₂ and % mobility change.

	PM ₁₀	NO ₂
Spearman's rho	0.364	0.692
p value	<0.001	<0.001

670

671 **Appendix B**

672 Spearman's rank correlation test was employed to analyze the relationship between meteorological
673 variables and noise indicators, as well as between meteorological variables and atmospheric chemical
674 pollutants.

675

676 **Table 9** Spearman's correlation among the noise indicators and meteorological parameters.

		Point 1				Point 2				Point 3			
		L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}	L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}	L_d	L_e	L_n	L_{den}
Temperature	rho	-0.085	-0.085	0.210	-0.009	-0.117	-0.427	0.251	-0.245	0.156	-0.139	0.323	0.178
	p	n.s.	n.s.	<0.05	n.s.	n.s.	<0.001	<0.01	<0.01	n.s.	n.s.	<0.01	n.s.
Precipitation	rho	-0.251	-0.262	-0.382	-0.333	-0.137	0.052	-0.272	-0.053	0.028	0.204	-0.107	-0.241
	p	<0.01	<0.01	<0.001	<0.001	n.s.	n.s.	<0.01	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	<0.05
Wind speed	rho	0.012	-0.003	-0.049	-0.006	0.038	0.050	0.028	0.027	0.169	0.154	0.086	0.174
	p	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Sunshine hours	rho	0.058	0.071	0.238	0.094	-0.026	-0.252	0.304	-0.073	0.051	-0.121	0.339	0.325
	p	n.s.	n.s.	<0.01	n.s.	n.s.	<0.01	<0.001	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	<0.01	<0.01

677 n.s.: Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$)

678

679 **Table 10** Relationship between PM₁₀, NO₂ and meteorological parameters.

		PM ₁₀	NO ₂
Temperature	rho	0.480	-0.143
	<i>p</i>	<0.001	n.s.
Precipitation	rho	-0.414	-0.471
	<i>p</i>	<0.001	<0.001
Wind speed	rho	-0.090	-0.345
	<i>p</i>	n.s.	<0.001
Sunshine hours	rho	0.384	0.089
	<i>p</i>	<0.001	n.s.

680

681 **Appendix C**

682 Mean values of the noise indicators L_d , L_e and L_n during the stages considered.

683

684 **Table 11** Mean values of the noise indicators L_d , L_e and L_n along with the standard error of the mean, for
685 the three measurement points, during the various stages considered for weekdays and weekends.

	Point 1					
	Weekdays			Weekend		
	L_d (dB)	L_e (dB)	L_n (dB)	L_d (dB)	L_e (dB)	L_n (dB)
Stage A	62.6 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	60.2 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	54.7 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	59.8 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	61.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	52.8 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}
Stage B	59.3 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	57.2 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	47.7 ^{+1.2} _{-0.9}	56.1 ^{+0.6} _{-0.8}	60.1 ^{+1.1} _{-1.4}	47.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}
Stage C	57.3 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	55.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	45.7 ^{+1.0} _{-1.3}	55.0 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	58.3 ^{+1.9} _{-3.4}	47.9 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}
Stage D	59.9 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	57.7 ^{+1.5} _{-2.3}	49.0 ^{+1.5} _{-2.4}	56.3 ^{+0.7} _{-0.9}	59.6 ^{+1.2} _{-1.6}	46.5 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}
Stage E	60.2 ^{+1.3} _{-1.9}	56.0 ^{+0.7} _{-0.9}	46.2 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	56.4 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	59.6 ^{+1.7} _{-2.8}	47.0 ^{+0.8} _{-1.0}
Stage F	68.0 ^{+1.1} _{-1.4}	55.1 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	47.6 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	55.9 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	56.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	48.3 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}
Stage G	62.5 ^{+1.4} _{-1.1}	58.5 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	51.1 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	56.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	59.4 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	51.3 ^{+0.8} _{-1.0}
Stage H	60.6 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	59.3 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	54.2 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	57.3 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	59.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	52.2 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}
Stage I	61.2 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	60.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	56.2 ^{+1.2} _{-1.7}	59.5 ^{+0.6} _{-0.5}	60.6 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	53.1 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}
Stage J	61.4 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	59.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	56.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	58.2 ^{+1.0} _{-1.3}	60.5 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	53.4 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}

686

	Point 2					
	Weekdays			Weekend		
	L_d (dB)	L_e (dB)	L_n (dB)	L_d (dB)	L_e (dB)	L_n (dB)
Stage A	59.9 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	59.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	49.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	57.7 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	57.8 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	49.8 ^{+0.8} _{-1.0}
Stage B	57.0 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	62.1 ^{+1.2} _{-1.7}	46.4 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	54.5 ^{+1.1} _{-1.4}	61.1 ^{+1.4} _{-2.2}	47.4 ^{+1.9} _{-3.3}
Stage C	57.0 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	62.0 ^{+1.4} _{-2.1}	47.8 ^{+0.8} _{-0.9}	53.8 ^{+1.6} _{-2.7}	60.8 ^{+1.4} _{-2.0}	43.2 ^{+1.0} _{-1.3}
Stage D	56.8 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	62.7 ^{+1.0} _{-1.2}	46.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	54.5 ^{+1.2} _{-1.7}	58.2 ^{+0.9} _{-1.1}	45.9 ^{+0.8} _{-1.0}
Stage E	56.8 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	57.0 ^{+1.4} _{-2.0}	47.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	53.6 ^{+1.8} _{-3.1}	56.6 ^{+1.1} _{-1.6}	43.6 ^{+1.7} _{-2.8}
Stage F	56.7 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	54.8 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	47.1 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	54.9 ^{+2.0} _{-3.8}	53.6 ^{+1.1} _{-1.4}	45.5 ^{+2.2} _{-4.8}
Stage G	57.6 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	56.0 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	48.3 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	55.6 ^{+1.0} _{-1.2}	55.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	47.2 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}

Stage H	57.4 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	57.2 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	48.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	57.4 ^{+1.0} _{-1.3}	56.9 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	49.3 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}
Stage I	57.9 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	58.0 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	50.2 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	56.4 ^{+0.8} _{-1.0}	57.0 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	50.7 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}
Stage J	58.2 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	58.4 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	52.3 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	56.3 ^{+1.4} _{-2.1}	57.1 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	52.6 ^{+0.8} _{-0.9}

687

Point 3						
	Weekdays			Weekend		
	L_d (dB)	L_e (dB)	L_n (dB)	L_d (dB)	L_e (dB)	L_n (dB)
Stage A	58.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	56.9 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	51.5 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	55.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	56.2 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	53.5 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}
Stage B	56.3 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	61.7 ^{+1.3} _{-1.9}	51.9 ^{+0.7} _{-0.9}	54.5 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	57.2 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	49.9 ^{+1.1} _{-1.6}
Stage C	55.5 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	59.3 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	50.7 ^{+0.7} _{-0.9}	55.9 ^{+0.6} _{-0.8}	60.6 ^{+1.0} _{-1.4}	48.7 ^{+1.7} _{-2.7}
Stage D	57.5 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	59.4 ^{+0.7} _{-0.9}	50.3 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	56.1 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	58.8 ^{+0.9} _{-1.2}	49.2 ^{+0.8} _{-1.0}
Stage E	57.0 ^{+0.6} _{-0.6}	60.2 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	49.7 ^{+1.3} _{-1.9}	56.9 ^a	61.5 ^a	57.8 ^a
Stage F						
Stage G						
Stage H	55.6 ^a	57.1 ^a		53.2 ^{+0.2} _{-0.2}	55.8 ^{+1.1} _{-1.4}	54.8 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}
Stage I	57.9 ^{+0.5} _{-0.5}	57.3 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	52.4 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	55.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	57.0 ^{+0.9} _{-1.1}	55.1 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}
Stage J	56.7 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	57.5 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	53.6 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	56.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.4}	58.1 ^{+0.5} _{-0.6}	51.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}

688 ^a There was only one value for this stage.

689

690 **Appendix D**

691 The actual values measured of L_{den} on the days prior to the declaration of the state of alarm were compared
 692 with three estimates considered for L_{den} .

693

694

(a)

695

(b)

696

(c)

697 **Fig. 8** Differences between the actual values of L_{den} during stage A and the different estimates considered
 698 for the three points: (a) Point 1; (b) Point 2; (c) Point 3.

699

700 **Table 12** Some statistical parameters for the differences between the real values of L_{den} during stage A and
 701 the different estimates considered for the three points. Abs() stand for the absolute value of the differences.
 702 Min: minimum difference; max: maximum difference, SD: standard deviation.

	estimate 1	abs(estimate 1)	estimate 2	abs(estimate 2)	estimate 3
Point 1					
min	-1.0	0.0	-1.2	0.0	0.5
max	0.8	1.0	1.3	1.3	2.3
range	1.9	1.0	2.4	1.3	1.8
mean	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.4	1.3
SD	0.4	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.4
Point 2					
min	-1.0	0.0	-1.5	0.0	0.8
max	1.1	1.1	1.4	1.5	2.9

range	2.1	1.1	2.9	1.5	2.0
mean	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.5	1.6
SD	0.4	0.3	0.7	0.4	0.4
Point 3					
min	-0.3	0.0	-0.6	0.1	0.3
max	0.4	0.4	0.9	0.9	1.5
range	0.7	0.4	1.5	0.9	1.2
mean	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.4	0.7
SD	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.4

703

704 Appendix E

705 Values established by the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge of the Spanish
706 government and for the WHO for air quality.

707

708 **Table 13** Air quality values established by the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic
709 Challenge of the Spanish government (2020)

PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	NO ₂ (µg/m ³)	Index category
0–20	0–40	Good
21–40	41–90	Reasonably good
41–50	91–120	Fair
51–100	121–230	Unfavourable
101–150	231–340	Very unfavourable
151–1200	341–1000	Extremely unfavourable

710

711 **Table 14** Air quality values established by the WHO (2021)

Pollutant	Averaging period	WHO guideline 2021
		(µg/m ³)
PM ₁₀	Annual	15
	24 h	45
NO ₂	Annual	10
	24 h	25

712

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714

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